

On new dynamic channel assignment schemes and their efficient evaluation through a generic simulation system for large scale cellular telecommunications

P.M Papazoglou⁽¹⁾, D.A. Karras, *Assoc. Member IEEE*⁽²⁾, and R.C. Papademetriou, *Member IEEE*^{(3)*}

Abstract - The rapid evolution of cellular technology and the augmentative user demand for advanced mobile services leads the industry to develop more efficient network structures. The increasing number of cellular users and the demand for broadband mobile communications (3rd and 4th generation) drives to the research of new methodologies for the design of cellular networks and services. Simulation environments more than ever offer the opportunity to develop and study with low cost new structures and methods for the implementation of new services. This paper thoroughly reviews centralized and distributed Dynamic Channel Assignment (DCA) schemes in terms of simulation characteristics and needs and proposes a comprehensive simulation system for evaluating them, which incorporates their principles, entities and concepts involved. The main goal, however, is to present three new DCA variations and prove - through experimental evaluation using the proposed simulation system - that the suggested schemes outperform traditional DCA schemes. The proposed simulation system is implemented in Java, in order to create a high performance generic simulation environment with the future capability of internetworking. The system is designed with the goal to be efficient in simulating large scale generic cellular telecommunication systems and the associated DCA schemes. Moreover, another goal of the proposed system is to serve as a test bed for the evaluation and development of DCA schemes (especially for educational purposes) involved in such large scale cellular systems towards their planning as effective cellular mobile radio networks.

Keywords - cellular networks, DCA variations, simulation models, channel allocation schemes.

I. INTRODUCTION

The concept of cellular networks

The cellular principle divides the covered geographical area into a set of smaller service areas called cells. Each cell has a base station and a number of mobile terminals (e.g. mobile phone, palms, laptops, or other mobile devices). The base station is equipped with radio transmission and reception equipment. The mobile terminal within a cell communicates through wireless links with the base station associated with the cell. A number of base stations are connected to the Base Station Controller (BSC) via microwave links or dedicated leased lines. The BSC contains logic for radio resource management of the base stations under its control. It is also responsible for transferring an ongoing call from one base station to another as a mobile user moves from cell to cell. In order to establish a communication with a base station, a mobile terminal must first obtain a channel from the base station. A channel consists of a pair of frequencies: one frequency (the forward link/downlink) for transmission from the base station to the mobile terminal, and another frequency (the reverse link/uplink) for the transmission in the reverse direction. An allocated channel is released under two scenarios: the user completes the call or the mobile user moves to another cell before the call is completed.

⁽¹⁾Lamia Institute of Technology, Greece and ECE Dept., University of Portsmouth, UK (e_mail: papaz@teilam.gr)

⁽²⁾Chalkis Institute of Technology, Greece and Hellenic Open University, Greece (e_mails: dakarras@teihal.gr, dakarras@ieec.org)

⁽³⁾ECE Dept., University of Portsmouth, UK (e_mail: rallis.papademetriou@port.ac.uk)

The need of Simulation systems in cellular networks

The performance and the behavior of a real cellular network can be evaluated using simulation systems without the need to perform field experiments and develop prototypes.

The simulation solutions give us the opportunity to develop custom protocols, channel allocation schemes, network structures, etc, towards to a desired cellular network.

Due to the complexity of real cellular networks the simulation software development strategy becomes a very important factor that influences the resulted network model. The structure of the simulation environment affects the performance of simulated cellular network and for that reason we try to study the design and the development of such system.

Many approaches to simulation systems have been made using general purpose languages, general simulation languages and special purpose simulation packages. General purpose languages have low cost, are portable and no additional training is needed but every model starts from scratch, verification is difficult, code reusability is low and the model development cycle is long. General simulation languages offer standardized features for modeling, shorter development cycle and easy verification. Such languages have higher cost, limited portability and additional training is needed. Languages such as Simula[1], Parsec[2], GPSS[3], Simgen[4], modsim[5], slam[6] and other of special purpose offer high flexibility for simulation systems development but introduce lack of portability and low adaptability to specific application models. Other software tools like Matlab, have a plethora of scientific libraries and capabilities for flexible script code development but suffer from low performance execution. A Large scale simulation system requires a flexible network environment with advanced characteristics such as portability, internetworking and high adaptability to the real network behavior.

The invention of new simulation languages introduce important drawbacks which are:

- New languages are domain-specific and are rarely adapted by scientific community
- The corresponding libraries impose the designers to adapt their applications in specific requirements
- Designers can not achieve high adaptability of the simulation kernel in their applications

Java language is the most suitable for building flexible, portable and high performance network applications and is adapted by the majority of scientific community.

With this simulation program, we attempt to build a generic simulation system for cellular communication systems of 3rd towards 4th generation in order to perform simulations not in ad-hoc systems as most software tools do. With a generic simulation system, clear and general conclusions can be extracted compared to ad-hoc wireless networks.

II. AN OVERVIEW OF CHANNEL ALLOCATION SCHEMES & GOS CONSIDERATION

The capacity of a cellular system can be described in terms of the number of available channels, or the number of users the system can support. The total number of channels made available to a system depends on the allocated spectrum and the bandwidth of each channel. The available frequency spectrum is limited and the number of mobile users is increasing day by day, hence the channels must be reused as much as possible to increase the system capacity. The assignment of channels to cells or mobile is one of the fundamental resource management issues in a mobile communication system. The role of a channel assignment scheme is to allocate channels to cells or mobiles in such a way as to minimize: a) the probability that the incoming calls are dropped, b) the probability that ongoing calls are dropped, and c) the probability that the carrier-to-interference ratio of any call falls below a prespecified value. In literature, many channel assignment schemes have been widely investigated with a goal to maximize the frequency reuse. The channel assignment schemes in general can be classified into three strategies: Fixed Channel Assignment (FCA) [7,8, 9,10,11], Dynamic Channel Assignment (DCA) [7,12,13,14,15], and the Hybrid Channel Assignment (HCA) [7,16]. In FCA, a set of channels are permanently allocated to each cell based on a pre-estimated traffic intensity. In DCA, there is no permanent allocation of channels to cells. Rather, the entire set of available channels is

accessible to all the cells, and the channels are assigned on a call-by-call basis in a dynamic manner. One of the objectives in DCA is to develop a channel assignment strategy, which minimizes the total number of blocked calls. The FCA scheme is simple but does not adapt to changing traffic conditions and user distribution. Moreover, the frequency planning becomes more difficult in a microcellular environment as it is based on the accurate knowledge of traffic and interference conditions. These deficiencies are overcome by DCA but FCA outperforms most known DCA schemes under heavy load conditions [8]. To overcome the drawbacks of FCA and DCA, HCA was proposed by Kahwa et al.[7], which combines the features of both FCA and DCA techniques. DCA schemes can be implemented as centralized or distributed. In the centralized approach [7] all requests for channel allocation are forwarded to a channel controller that has access to system wide channel usage information. The central controller then assigns the channel by maintaining the required signal quality. In distributed DCA [12], the decision regarding the channel acquisition and release is taken by the concerned base station on the basis of the information from the surrounding cells. As the decision is not based on the global status of the network, it can achieve only suboptimal allocation compared to the centralized DCA and may cause forced termination of ongoing calls. Many channel allocation schemes have been proposed. There are many variations of the FCA, DCA and HCA schemes.

FCA variations

Channel borrowing and non borrowing schemes

In channel borrowing schemes [17], a cell can borrow a channel from an adjacent cell only if there is no free channel in initial cell. After the use of the borrowed channel, the channel returns to its initial cell. Known schemes in channel borrowing category [17] are the Simple borrowing (SB), Borrow from the Richest (BFR) and Borrow First Available (BFA) scheme. In SB, after the initial channel assignment in each cell if there is no free channel for a new call, the needed channel can be borrowed from a neighboring cell. In the case of the BFR scheme, the available channel is borrowed from a neighboring cell that holds the greatest number of free channels (for borrowing) compared to other neighboring cells. Without any optimization when borrowing, BFA scheme is the simplest because the borrowing is based on the first available channel [17].

When the cell channels are divided in two groups – standard channels and borrowable channels – we have the Simple Complex Channel Borrowing Scheme (SCCB). In Borrowing with Channel Ordering (BCO) we use channel priorities to define the borrowing order. Other FCA variations are Sharing with Bias (SHB), channel Assignment with Borrowing and Reassignment (CABR), and Ordered Dynamic Channel Assignment with Rearrangement (ODCA) [18].

Non borrowing schemes are mostly based on hand-off strategies where an available channel is difficult to locate.

DCA variations

As we mentioned before, centralized and distributed versions are the main variations of the DCA scheme.

Centralized DCA schemes

The First Available (FA) is the simplest method where the first available channel within the reuse distance encountered during a channel search is assigned to the new call. Future blocking probability is a very important factor for the channel selection in a new call. Locally Optimized Dynamic Assignment (LODA) examines this probability in order to assign a new channel. The Mean Square (MSQ) scheme selects an available channel that minimizes the MSQ between cells that use the same channel.

Distributed DCA schemes

The distributed DCA schemes are based on signal quality computations around the initiated calls. More precisely, are based on co-channel distance, signal strength measurement and signal to noise interference ratio. Locally Optimized Least Interference DCA algorithm (LOLIA) [19] is a known variation and computes the interference among users that use the same channel and examines the signal quality in comparison with a defined threshold.

One of the most important characteristic of a cellular network is that a certain number of calls will fail to establish an initial connection. We can state two measures for dealing with unsuccessful call attempts: the never serviced new calls, and the delayed successful calls (waiting for initial connection).

The service quality in the busy period of the day may be expressed as the grade of service [20] or quality of service. Two requirements can be set in order to measure GoS level or Quality of Service [21]:

- GoS, loss system : probability of blocking $< x\%$
- GoS, delay system : probability (waiting time $> z$ sec) $< x\%$

Another quality metric can be the signal to noise interference $C/(N+I)$ ratio compared to a predefined threshold for the acceptability of a call. Carrier to noise ratio is a key performance for the networks and represents the signal strength against the channel noise. Another factor that degrades the carrier signal except the noise is the interference from other connected users that use the same frequency channel. If we increase the signal power to improve communication quality we increase in the same time the interference to other connected users. Thus, we introduce Carrier to Noise plus Interference Ratio, $C/(N+I)$, that represents the signal strength (quality) against noise and interference from other connected users.[22, 23]

III. THE PROPOSED GENERIC SIMULATION SYSTEM

Our system is a generic simulation system for cellular communications of 3rd and towards 4th generation in order to perform simulations not only in ad-hoc wireless networks but in every cellular network.

The number of communication channels, the number of users and other simulation parameters can be configured using a special configuration text file. The supported channel allocation schemes for a given cellular network are distributed DCA and centralized DCA. As we mentioned in previous section, the whole program was built in Java in order to have the capability of future extensions in any constrains.

In order to build a sufficient simulation system it is necessary to take in consideration some basic aspects of the operation of the cellular network which are:

User characteristics - user attributes including connection status, current position, call holding time, allocated channel, communication signal strength and interference (if necessary), etc.

Network parameters - Cells number, channels per cell, cell positions, base station positions, etc.

Traffic and QoS - new call arrival schemes, user movement profile, call dropping conditions, hand-of conditions, etc.

Channel allocation schemes – channel allocation strategy according to network conditions, congestions cases, resources limitations, etc.

Our simulation system consists of one main module - the simulation module, and nine additional modules. The additional modules are used for the necessary computations, the network model structure and simulation program execution.

Traditional DCA schemes that are used in our simulation system

In distributed DCA, the call management is based on the desired Carrier to noise interference $C/(N+I)$ ratio. For the centralized DCA scheme the first available channel is allocated to the new user in the cell only if the channel is not used in any other adjacent cell.

The network structure

The cellular network consists of N cells and each of the cells includes a base station in the center position (fig.1). Around the N cells there are some copied cells (from real cells) in order to generate the expected behavior when users exist in boundary cells.

Figure 1 - structure of the cellular network model

Each cell is divided in a mesh of spots (fig.2) where the users may exist from the beginning of the call or due to hand-of situation. The number of spots per cell mesh can be defined from the simulation configuration. The basic parameter for the mesh construction is the fineness which means the distance between the spots.

Figure 2 - cell mesh (possible user positions in a cell)

According to user conditions, the simulation program saves the relevant information in the user attribute table. These attributes summarize the user conditions and updated in every user new state (Table 1).

User attribute	Description
X position	Current X position in the network
Y position	Current Y position in the network
Connection status	0=no connected, 1=connected
Call holding time	Call termination time (sec)
Allocated channel	Allocated channel (if connected)
Path loss	Path loss of the user (if connected)

Table 1 - user attributes

The simulation takes place during the simulation time. In this time, several procedures are executed:

- call termination check
- reallocation check
- new call arrival
- user movement

There are also additional procedures for the normal operation of the simulation program, like configuration file processing, initialization, etc. The basic network parameters for the simulation procedure are GSM like and are summarized in table 2.

Network Parameters	Description
CNR on cell edge (dB)	Carrier to Noise Ratio in the cell edge
CNIR threshold (dB)	Accepted Carrier to Noise Ratio for a successful call
average call holding time (sec)	Call duration
channels per cell	Maximum available number of Channel pairs (upload/download) per cell
path loss factor(alpha)	Signal attenuation due to distance (signal path)
standard deviation of shadowing(sigma)	Shadowing attenuation
cellmesh fineness	Number of possible locations of a user in a cell
max users per cell	Maximum connected users per cell
No. of cells	Number of cells
New call arrival rate	Rate of new call occurrence
User movement rate	Rate of user movement occurrence

Table 2 – Network parameters for simulation

Main Simulation/Network procedures

Call termination. The program uses an exponential function that generates the call duration for each new user. The call holding time is added to current simulation time for later examination. The associated procedure scans the network cells and searches for any connected users and examines the progressive call time. If this time is expired the user attribute table is updated with the new connection status of the particular user both in distributed and centralized DCA. In addition, in centralized DCA the new free channel after the call termination returns in the channel pool. Figure 3a, shows the logic diagram of that algorithm.

Figure 3a
call termination
procedure

Figure 3b
Reallocation check
(distributed DCA)

Figure 3c
New call arrival
(distributed DCA)

Figure 3d
New call arrival
(centralized DCA)

Reallocation check (Distributed DCA)

The reallocation algorithm searches all the cells for connected users and performs check for each user (fig. 3b). The computations are based on signal strength and how is affected from other connected users in neighbor cells. If a user signal does not fulfill the $C/(N+I)$ threshold (Carrier to Noise and Interference ratio) the procedure tries to find another appropriate channel. The Carrier to Noise and Interference ratio can be derived using the type

$$R_{cni} = \frac{A P_0 d_0^{-\alpha} 10^{\frac{\xi_0}{10}}}{N + \sum_{i=1}^n A P_i d_i^{-\alpha} 10^{\frac{\xi_i}{10}}} \quad (1)$$

Where n is the number of base stations and users, ξ_i is the distortion due to shadowing from user to base station, A is a proportional coefficient, P_0 is the transmitted power of a reference point, P_i is the transmitted power of the i user and d_i is the distance between user i and reference base station. Firstly, the algorithm calculates the signal strength between user and base station and in later time calculates any interference from around connected users. If an accepted channel is found, is allocated to the new user, otherwise the call is dropped. The program searches for a channel according to the selected DCA scheme. In centralized version, the reallocation process searches for a free channel in the central channel pool.

New call arrival based on user profile

New calls are resulted from a random or a Poisson distribution with regard to a predefined daily model. The algorithm searches all the cells for not connected users (according to user attribute table). Each user belongs to a user profile with regard to the time of the day. When a new call arrival occurs with regard to Poisson distribution, the program gets a random number x from Poisson distribution and calculates the corresponding $P(x)$ which is :

$$P(x) = \frac{e^{-\lambda} \cdot \lambda^x}{x!} \quad (2)$$

Where λ represents the new call arrival rate. This rate is analogous to the time of the day. A fixed set of simulation time steps represents a whole day. Each day is divided in to five zones according to traffic conditions. Each zone represents a specific percentage period of the day. The parameter λ , changes with regard to each active zone in simulation time. Table 3, illustrates the five zones with corresponding λ parameter.

zone	Zone (approximately)	percentage	λ	Description
1		34%	1	Least busy zone
2		21%	4	
3		12%	5	Most busy zone
4		17%	3	
5		17%	2	

Table 3. Daily zones

Zone 1, may represents the hours 12-9am ($\lambda=1$) and zone 3 the hours 1-4pm ($\lambda=5$). Finally, the number of users to be connected in each cell is analogous to x , it is based on $P(x)$ and never exceeds the maximum limit of users that is calculated by the daily model. If proper conditions exist for a new call arrival, a random position in the cell mesh is calculated. The user position attribute is updated with the mesh spot position in combination with the position of the base station in the center of the cell.

Channel Allocation

The signal strength is calculated between the new user and the base station. Channel allocation is successful if a free channel is found in the cell and the $C/(N+I)$ constraint is fulfilled (fig.4).

After a new call arrival, several actions take place in turn (fig. 4a):

- a) Search for unconnected users in each cell
- b) Calculate a random user position in the mesh
- c) Place the new user according to cell's base station position and mesh spot
- d) Calculate the signal strength between base station and new user

Firstly we obtain the shadow attenuation [22,23] as

$$sh = 10^{\frac{\sigma \cdot n}{10}} \quad (3)$$

where σ is the standard deviation of shadowing and n is a number from the normal distribution. Using the shadow attenuation and distance between user and base station, we can derive the distance attenuation dw . Finally, we calculate the CNIR (Carrier to Noise Interference Ratio) between user and base station [22,23]

$$cn = 10^{\frac{cnedge}{10}} \cdot dw \quad (4)$$

where $cnedge$ is the CNR on cell edge (dB).

e) Scan the other cells and calculate interference among new user and other users that use the same channel

f) Check if $C/(N+I)$ ratio is acceptable according to predefined threshold

g) If $C/(N+I)$ is acceptable, establish the new call and update the table of user attributes.

New call arrival and channel allocation (centralized DCA)

A new call arrival occurs under the same conditions in distributed DCA. After the calculation of new user position, the algorithm searches for an available channel that is not used in current cell or in any adjacent cell. The search is performed using the channel pool that keeps information for channel usage all over the cellular network. The channel allocation criterion is based only in the channel usage

in adjacent cells. This method requires less processing power than the method in distributed DCA because is not based to mathematical calculations.

User movement (distributed & Centralized DCA)

The simulation program supports two types of user movement. The first type of user movement is based on random number generation like new call arrival and the second on Gaussian distribution. The algorithm locates the connected users and changes their current positions. The reallocation procedure in distributed DCA checks the new user positions and performs new channel assignment if needed. In centralized DCA, after user movement, the user is disconnected and the algorithm searches for a proper free channel from the central channel pool.

The Gaussian distribution density function is

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-(x-\mu)^2/2\sigma^2} \tag{5}$$

, where σ is the standard deviation and μ is the mean value. The Gaussian distribution in our program has mean value zero and standard deviation one. Hence, the density function becomes

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-x^2/2} \tag{6}$$

In the user movement procedure, firstly we generate a Gaussian number e.g. x_1 and the corresponding $f(x_1)$ when $x_1 \in [-0.5, 0.5]$. If another Gaussian number e.g. x_2 , where $|x_2| \geq f(x_1)$ a user move is generated.

III. THE PROPOSED DCA VARIATIONS

We have used our simulation program to evaluate the new proposed DCA variations which are:

- Balanced version (based on least-congested algorithm around neighbors)
- Best CNR version (based on strongest CNR around neighbors)
- Round blocking version (based on unbalanced DCA version around neighbors)

Firstly, the program tries to assign a channel within the initiated cell of the new call and afterwards activates any of the above methods.

The above mentioned procedures such as reallocation, new call arrival and user movement are adapted each time to the selected DCA variation (e.g. balanced, unbalanced, round blocking, etc)

Balanced variation (min cell congestion)

The DCA unbalanced algorithm assigns the first channel that fulfills the conditions and the DCA balanced uses the least congestion algorithm for the completion of channel assignment.

As we mentioned before, the balanced method uses the least congested algorithm. Initially, we assume that the least congested cell is the cell where the new call is occurred. The algorithm scans all the cells sequentially in the neighbor region and finds the least congested cell (fig. 4a). For example, cell number 7 (figure 4b), contains only 4 users compared to other cells in the neighbor and so is the least congested cell.

Figure 4a – The least congestion algorithm (Balanced variation)

Figure 4b – The least congestion Logic

Best CNR variation

The best CNR method goes around the six neighbor cells of the initiated cell and calculates the CNR between user and neighbor cell base stations. After the strongest CNR is found, the program tries to assign a new channel from the corresponding cell. The algorithm initially assumes that the strongest CNR exists from the first neighbor cell and continues to calculate CNR from the rest neighbor cells sequentially until the strongest CNR is found. Figure 5a and 5b, illustrates the algorithm structure and logic respectively.

Figure 5a – The Best CNR algorithm

Figure 5b – The Best CNR Logic

Round Blocking variation

The round blocking algorithm searches in neighbor cells and when a successful channel assignment is made the algorithm stops. If the call establishment is not successful in the last neighbor cell, the call is blocked. Figure 6a and 6b shows the round blocking algorithm and the logic respectively.

Figure 6a – The Round Blocking algorithm

Figure 6b – The Round Blocking Logic

Unbalanced variation

Unbalanced variation represents the traditional DCA scheme where only one attempt (in call initiating cell)for connection is done based on the Carrier to Noise plus interference criterion (fig. 7).

Figure 7 – Traditional DCA algorithm (Unbalanced)

Basic Statistical metrics

The blocking probability is one of the most important characteristics for the performance of a cellular network. When a new call arrival occurs and the network can not allocate a channel then we say that this call is blocked. The blocking probability P_{bl} is calculated from the ratio

$$P_{blocking} = \frac{\text{number of blocked calls}}{\text{number of calls}} \quad (7)$$

If the received power of each user is high enough, we can make the assumption that the interference from other users can be ignored. Thus, we can compare the simulated blocking probability with the theoretical which is

$$P_{blocking_theoretical} = \frac{\binom{n-1}{s} (vh)^s}{\sum_{i=0}^s \binom{n-1}{i} (vh)^i} \quad (8)$$

where n is the number of users, s is the number of channels, v is the average call arrival rate (for no connected user) and h is the average call holding time.

The *dropping probability* is also an additional and very important characteristic of the cellular network. When a call is in progress and the required quality conditions are not met then this call is obligatory driven to termination. The dropping probability P_{fc} is calculated from the ratio

$$P_{forced\ calls} = \frac{\text{number of forced calls}}{\text{number of calls} - \text{number of blocked calls}} \quad (9)$$

We have used several basic statistical metrics such as Standard deviation, Mean Value and Variance in the experimental section of this paper.

Experimental results

The system produces the simulation results in matlab files (.m files) for later process in matlab. Each result file contains the simulation data and the appropriate matlab commands for graph viewing and statistical analysis.

The simulation results include data for calculating important measures such as blocking probability, dropping probability, channel reuse, cell congestion, number of reallocations, channel reuse per cell, etc.

The generated matlab files include additional commands for calculating several statistical metrics of simulation results like Standard deviation, Covariance and Average values.

Indicative results

As we mentioned before, the simulation system produces a variety of graphs. Figure 8, shows the channel reusability per network cell of an example network. The example network consists of 19 cells, 100 users per cell, 32 channels per cell and uses the distributed DCA scheme.

Figure 8 – channel reusability

The daily model that we have used divides the whole simulation time in five days respectively. The blocking probability varies among the hours of each day (fig.9).

Figure 9 - blocking probability

Next figure (fig. 10) shows the dropping probability with regard to traffic conditions based on mentioned daily model for the example network.

Figure 10 - Dropping probability

DCA comparative results

We have simulated a cellular network of 19 cells capacity with 10, 50, 80,100,200,400,750 users per cell and 5, 32 channels per cell respectively. The simulation results are divided in two categories :

- Unbalanced Distributed and Centralized DCA (traditional Channel Allocation)
- Distributed DCA with the three proposed variations

In Centralized DCA scheme, the new call arrival and user movement procedures are based in random distribution. In addition, in distributed DCA scheme, the new call arrival is based on random distribution and user movement is based on random or Gaussian distribution. Figure 11 shows the blocking probability for Distributed and Centralized DCA. The Centralized scheme is very inflexible as the number of users is increasing compared to other Distributed schemes. With user movement or not, Centralized DCA can not be adapted to the user load.

Figure 11. Blocking probability of various DCA schemes (5 channels per cell)
 nm/m=no user movement/user movement,
 crr=centralized DCA, random call arrival, random user movement (in m categories)
 drr=distributed, DCA, random call arrival, random user movement (in m categories),
 drg= distributed DCA, random call arrival, Gaussian user movement (in m categories)

Figure 12 illustrates that even with 32 channels per cell, the centralized DCA schemes are still inflexible to higher user load.

Figure 12. Blocking probability of various DCA schemes (32 channels per cell)

Figure 12, confirms the previous note about the performance of Centralized DCA in small networks and shows that even with more available channels per cell the Centralized DCA is not satisfactory for small networks. The above figures also show that the user movement and user movement distribution plays important role for the network behavior.

In Centralized DCA the number of cell congestions is smaller in contrast with Distributed DCA (fig.13 & 14) and that means that the network management is easiest is centralized DCA.

Figure 13 - cell congestions (5 channels)

Figure 14 - cell congestions (32 channels)

The three proposed DCA variations, perform better than the traditional DCA under heavy user load (fig.15). In traditional DCA scheme only one attempt for connection is done within the current cell. On the contrary, in all the three proposed variations several attempts for connection are made among the adjacent cells. The best CNR algorithm it seems to be the most appropriate for channel allocation because ensures the strongest CNR between user and base station and so higher shield from interference is achieved.

Fig 15. Blocking probability of the traditional DCA scheme and the three proposed Schemes

Fig 16. Dropping probability of the traditional DCA scheme and the three proposed Schemes

The dropping probability (fig. 16) with regard to proposed variations is lower than the traditional DCA scheme. Although, in high user loads, all the DCA schemes seem to have the same behavior because there are a large number of users compared to available channels in the cell.

V. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

There is no doubt that cellular network simulation is a very complicated procedure. From the point of view of network designer the development and research of various channel allocation schemes must be faced from the lowest starting point. The type and the number of parameters that the designer should take in consideration depend on the type of the network and the procedure focusing inside the network. The divergence between simulation results and real network behavior is affected by the structure of the implementation algorithms and the corresponding research of real network conditions, like new call arrival schemes, user movement, etc. A deeper research requires full customizable software with high level of adaptation in real network specifications and behavior.

In this paper we have presented a generic simulation environment for GSM cellular networks and also several DCA variations for efficient channel assignment. We have clearly shown through thorough experimental results that our proposed DCA variations perform better than the traditional DCA

scheme and, moreover, they could be efficiently evaluated through the proposed generic simulation system.

Our future goal is to develop a simulation system for large scale generic cellular networks using other implementation architectures in order to extract clearer and reliable conclusions for real world DCA algorithm behavior and performance. With the internetworking capability of Java language, our simulation system might be, also, used for educational purposes too. In order to develop an efficient and useful simulation environment we have to study the evolution, the specifications and the constraints of real cellular networks as well as to investigate the algorithmic schemes that might be used, like multi-threading, for the user and network model, etc.

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Hellenic European Research on Mathematics and Informatics Science (HERMIS - $\mu\pi$)

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The main purpose of the Hellenic European Research on Mathematics and Informatics Science (HERMIS- $\mu\pi$) Journal is to present original research work of the highest quality and characteristic representative samples of the current trends in various directions of research being done in the areas of Computer Mathematics and its Applications. The topics covered in this issue encompass different aspects of such subjects.

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Athens, Hellas
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